

Wikibase instances in the Cultural Heritage Domain: Examples from the German humanities NFDI consortia

Florian Thiery, Lozana Rossenova, Olaf Simons

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Session: Cultural Heritage and the new future of new technologies

The German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)

The Humanities Memorandum Group in NFDI (Services)

Wikibase Use Cases in NFDI4Objects

Wikibase instances & Wikidata
in (Computational) Archaeology

Why Wikibases in NFDI4Objects?

Wikibase Usage Examples in NFDI4Objects

Provenance Gazetteer for persons & corporate bodies

NFDI4Objects

Create unique PIDs for persons / corporate bodies ...

[DOWNLOAD CSV](#) [API](#) [CONTACT](#) [ABOUT US](#) [DE](#) | [EN](#)

Münzkabinett
 Staatliche Museen zu Berlin

Münzkabinett Authority File Portal

[HOME](#) [MK BERLIN](#)

Person ND

Name Lederer, Dr. Philipp (25.08.1872 - 02.09.1944)

Coin dealer in Berlin.

Numismatist and coin dealer from 1911 (or 1910?), previously from 1898 employed by J. Hirsch in Munich.

Lederer wrote his Phd on the coinage of Segesta in 1910.

National service from September 1915, served as private in the Baltics. Return to Berlin in early 1919.

Lederer's office was opposite the Kaiser-Friedrich-Museum (now Bode-Museum) at the Kupfergraben.

H. A. Cahn's obituary stresses Lederer's good relationship with the Berlin Museums even after 1933.

Lederer was forced to emigrate to Switzerland following the events of November 1938.

Lit.: K. Priese, Berliner Münzhandel, BBPN 21, 2013, pp. 252; Obituary, BNZ 1950/51, pp. 148-149; H. A. Cahn, Obituary, SNR 32, 1946, pp. 69-73; J. Schwartz, Scheinbare Sicherheit - Geschäftsbeziehungen Philipp Lederers und seine NS-Verfolgungsgeschichte in: J. Schwartz - S. Voigt (eds.), Spuren der NS-Verfolgung. Provenienzforschung in den kulturhistorischen Sammlungen der Stadt Hannover (2019) pp. 137-159, esp. 138-139, 142, 145.

Types Design ND, Vendor (to Museum) ND, Vendor (to prev. Owner) ND

GND <https://d-nb.info/gnd/143778765> id

Wikipedia [de] https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Philipp_Lederer w

VIAF <https://viaf.org/viaf/103209084> id

<https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/term/BIOG59166> i

Wikidata <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q2086982> w

Permalink <https://ikmk.smb.museum/ndp/person/4077>

- Main page
- Recent changes
- Random page
- Help about Wikibase
- Tools
- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Printable version
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concept URI
- Wikibase
- New Item
- New Property
- New Schema
- All Properties
- Query Service
- Cradle
- QuickStatements

In other languages [Add links](#)

Item [Discussion](#)

Dr. Philipp Lederer (Q25)

Coin Dealer in Berlin

▼ In more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Dr. Philipp Lederer	Coin Dealer in Berlin	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concept ▼ 0 references
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Person / Human ▼ 0 references
in scheme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Person-Gazetteer ▼ 0 references
has role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coin Dealer ▼ 0 references

via <https://ikmk.smb.museum/ndp/person/4077>

via <https://n4o-prov.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q25>

... link them to other resources in the WWW ...

Item Discussion

Dr. Philipp Lederer (Q25)

Coin Dealer in Berlin

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Dr. Philipp Lederer	Coin Dealer in Berlin	

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instance of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concept <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ 0 references Person / Human <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ 0 references
in scheme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Person-Gazetteer <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ 0 references
has role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coin Dealer <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ 0 references

aligned with

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://ikmk.smb.museum/ndp/person/4077 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> alignment type: exact match alignment repository: NDP ▼ 0 references
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://d-nb.info/gnd/143778765 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> alignment type: exact match alignment repository: GND ▶ 1 reference
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> http://viaf.org/viaf/103209084 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> alignment type: exact match alignment repository: VIAF ▶ 1 reference
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> http://wikidata.org/entity/Q2086982 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> alignment type: exact match alignment repository: Wikidata ▶ 1 reference
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Philipp_Lederer <ul style="list-style-type: none"> alignment type: exact match alignment repository: Wikipedia ▶ 1 reference
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/term/BIOG59166 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> alignment type: exact match alignment repository: British Museum ▶ 1 reference

via <https://n40-prov.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q25>

Modelling of Vagueness & Ambiguities

NFDI4Objects

Where is the Findspot at Urluia / Romania?

Fitzsimmons et al. (2014), p.76

“In this paper we investigate [...] the site of Urluia Quarry on the Dobrogea loess plateau [...], **some 15 km south of the Danube River**. The site immediately overlies the Quaternary-uplifted Cretaceous-Tertiary- age limestone basement rocks (Munteanu et al., 2008), which were the target of earlier quarrying activities.”

Pötter et al. (2021), p.5

“The Urluia (URL) LPS is **located in an abandoned limestone quarry on the limestone plateau of the Dobrogea** (Fitzsimmons et al., 2013; Fitzsimmons and Hambach, 2014; Obreht et al., 2017).”

Where is the Findspot at Urluia / Romania?

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

via <http://www.openstreetmap.org/way/84975654>

The Findspot *URLUIA* and Sources in the *fuzzy-sl* Wikibase

Item Discussion

Urluia Quarry (Q73)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot

↕ In more languages
Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Urluia Quarry	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot	

Statements

instance of Geological Site
↕ 0 references

has reference

- Fitzsimmons et al., 2014
↕ 0 references
- Fitzsimmons et al., 2013
↕ 0 references
- Obreht et al., 2017
↕ 0 references
- Pötter et al., 2021
↕ 0 references

related to

- http://openstreetmap.org/way/84975654
↕ 0 references
- http://sws.geonames.org/664132
↕ 0 references
- http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q13054772
↕ 0 references

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q73>

has coordinate 44°5'40.9"N, 27°54'7.6"E

certainty level Medium

certainty description Fitzsimmons et al. (2014), p.76: "In this paper we investigate [...] the site of Urluia Quarry on the Dobrogea loess plateau [...], some 15 km south of the Danube River. The site immediately overlies the Quaternary-uplifted Cretaceous-Tertiary-age limestone basement rocks (Munteanu et al., 2008), which were the target of earlier quarrying activities."; Pötter et al. (2021), p.5: "The Urluia (URL) LPS is located in an abandoned limestone quarry on the limestone plateau of the Dobrogea (Fitzsimmons et al., 2013; Fitzsimmons and Hambach, 2014; Obreht et al., 2017)."

method used Georeferencing

acting person Fiona Schenk

source type (detail) Paper

source type (generic) Textual Description

method description set a point based on Fitzsimmons et al. (2014), p.76 and Pötter et al. (2021), p.5 using OSM Way 84975654

precision ±0.0001°

location type Findspot

point type Location of a Place as a Concept

↕ 1 reference

- reference (String) Fitzsimmons et al. (2014), p.76
Pötter et al. (2021), p.5

Auel Maar & Dehner Maar sites in Schenk et al. (2024)

via <https://doi.org/10.3390/quat7020017>, Fig. 1

The Findspot *Auel AU3* and Sources in the *fuzzy-sl* Wikibase

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q70>

Item **Discussion**

Auel Maar AU3 (Q70)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot

▼ In more languages
Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Auel Maar AU3	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot	

Statements

instance of Geological Site
▼ 0 references

related to https://kulturdb.de/einobjekt.php?id=23391
related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch
▼ 0 references

has reference Schenk et al. (2024)
► 1 reference

part of Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots
▼ 0 references

has spatial type Maar
▼ 0 references

has coordinate 50°16'57.0"N, 6°35'42.4"E

certainty level High

certainty description stated in scientific paper, Schenk et al. (2024), fig. 1

method used Georeferencing

acting person Fiona Schenk

method description site survey

source type (detail) Paper

source type (generic) Textual Description

precision ±0.0001°

location type Findspot

point type Investigation Place

▼ 1 reference

reference URL https://doi.org/10.3390/quat7020017

via <https://doi.org/10.3390/quat7020017>, Fig. 1

Citizen Science & Wikidata

NFDI4Objects

The Linked Open Ogham LOD / Wikidata Workflow

This project is funded by Wikimedia Deutschland e. V. within the Open Science Fellows Program.

wmde.org/opensciencefellows

Florian Thiery, Timo Homburg, Sophie C. Schmidt und Martina Trognitz, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Ogham Sites in Wikidata

Wikidata Query Service

Beispiele Hilfe Weitere Werkzeuge Abfragegenerator

```
1 #defaultView:Map
2 # Ogham Sites
3 SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo WHERE {
4   ?item wdt:P361 wd:Q100530634;
5     wdt:P31 wd:Q72617071;
6     wdt:P625 ?geo.
7   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
8 }
```


via <https://wiki/6HMD>

FactGrid
a database for historians

Wikibase Use Cases in NFDI4Memory

FactGrid Project spaces

Extra-Europeans in Early Modern Europe [\[edit\]](#)

(Field of Research:Q464939) Text.

Project initiated by Anne Kuhlmann-Smirnov

- [Basic list](#) / [extended list with places of residence](#)
- [Timeline: People from other continents that have been spotted in FactGrid's Europe](#) (incomplete as a approximate birth dates still have to be given)
- [Where did they come from? \(map\)](#)
- [Gender distribution \(bar chart\)](#)

Subscription lists [\[edit\]](#)

Thousands of 18th- and 19th-century publications appeared with subscription lists of those who promised to buy copies as soon the title was printed. These lists are extremely valuable to understand the respective audiences to which these titles sounded appealing — they usually offer additional information about social status, place of home address, gender, occupation. FactGrid is an ideal medium to gather and aggregate such information as we are ready to create items even if we do not know more about the respective objects of knowledge. Create such objects and aggregate information in the research process...

The FactGrid Subscription project was started with data which [Martin Perkins](#) and [Simon D. I. Fleming](#) were providing on 768 musical publications published primarily for anglophone audiences in the long 18th century with a total of 156,172 subscriptions, see their page for first queries:

- [FactGrid:Musical Subscriptions](#)

Early Modern Societies and Academies [\[edit\]](#)

This is an open project. If you have a complete list of members of an Early Modern learned society or Academy, feed it into FactGrid and see how the members connect.

- [Die Ritter des Goldenen Vlieses](#) far from complete
- [Fruchtbringende Gesellschaft, 1617](#) / [Timeline \(entry date\)](#) complete
- [Aufrichtige Gesellschaft von der Tannen, 1633](#) incomplete
- [Deutschgesinnte Gesellschaft 1643](#) incomplete
- [Pegnesischer Blumenorden, 1644](#) incomplete

The FactGrid Prose Fiction Project [\[edit\]](#)

(Field of Research:Q195135) Early modern readers were expected to laugh about the medieval romances and legends that had flooded the European book market from the 1470s into 1570s with the help of the new printing presses. With a more sophisticated taste one could enjoy "satirical romances" and shorter "novels" — "romances", however, had become a precarious production. The alternative to all this fictionality was "literature", the field of learning.

Things began to change strangely in the course of the late 17th and early 18th centuries: The "belles lettres" had become an accepted part of "literature" in the fashionable centres of Paris, The Hague,

Tenants in Leipzig (1850)

Address [geolocated item]

Leipzig, Brühl 59 (7th rental property) 2. Treppe im Hintergebäude edit

Begin date 24 June 1845 *Gregorian*
End date 24 June 1847 *Gregorian*
Rent (per annum) 40 Reichs Thaler (Prussian 14 Taler standard of 1750)
Tax (per annum) 0.20 Reichs Thaler (Prussian 14 Taler standard of 1750)
Primary source [Municipal Archives Leipzig: Hauptbücher über die Beiträge zum Stadtschulden Tilgungsfonds, 0008 \(Ratsstube\), Nr. 3186/3187 \(1842-1853\)](#)

▼ 2 references

Primary source [Municipal Archives Leipzig: Hauptbücher über die Beiträge zum Stadtschulden Tilgungsfonds, 0008 \(Ratsstube\), Nr. 3186/3187 \(1842-1853\)](#)

Image number 133149c3

Wikimedia Commons Item image

Haus-Nr.	Anfang im Monat	Namen.	Mietz. jäh.	Jährliche Betrag.		Halbjährliche Abtragung.		Anmerkungen.
				1. Halbj.	2. Halbj.	1. Halbj.	2. Halbj.	
122		L. Kaufmann	10	5	5			

Tenants in Leipzig moving to the Gewandgässchen

Concentration and Extermination Camps (1930-1945)

Wikibase Use Cases in NFDI4Culture

Enrichment Open Source Tool Suite based on Wikibase

Data model for NFDI4Culture:

Integrating existing standards incl.

CIDOC-CRM, CRMdig & W3C Web Annotation Standard

Semantic Kompakt Service

British English Log in Request account

Item Discussion Read View history Search Semantic Kompakkt Wikiba Q

Weikersheim Dining Room 3D model (Q429)

A 3D reconstruction of the dining room and ceiling paintings

↳ In more languages

↳ Mapping to other ontologies

Predicate	URL
instance of	Media item ↳ 0 references
date	2021-07-22 (July 22nd, 2021) ↳ 0 references
creator	Jan Lutteroth ↳ 0 references
rightsowner	Corpus of baroque ceiling paintings in Germany ↳ 0 references
license	Creative Commons Attribution

British English Log in Request account

Item Discussion Read View history Search Semantic Kompakkt Wikiba Q

Fensterische Tafelstube Nord (Q435)

Annotation generated for Q429

↳ In more languages

↳ Mapping to other ontologies

Predicate	URL
instance of	Annotation ↳ 0 references
date	2022-12-16T18:00:51Z (18:00:51 UTC December 16th, 2022) ↳ 0 references

image

PreviewQ435.png
360 x 225; 31 KB
↳ 0 references

SEMANTIC KOMPAKKT Explore Annotate Login Register

Annotate

Fensterische Tafelstube Nord
Die Fensterische waren in Fortsetzung der Saaldekoration mit Roll- und Beschlagwerk stuckiert, wofür Christoph Limmerich in Frage kommt, der auch im Saal gearbeitet hat.

acanthus ~ ornament

Weikersheim Dining Room 3D model
A 3D reconstruction of the dining room and ceiling paintings

- Related agents
- Licence
- Creation
 - Technique: [digital 3D reconstruction](#)
 - Software: [Cinema 4D](#)
 - Date: 2021-07-21
- Related object structure
 - [Weikersheim castle complex](#)
 - ↳ [Weikersheim castle](#)
 - ↳ [Great hall \(Weikersheim\)](#)
 - ↳ [Access room sequences](#)
 - ↳ [Dining room](#)

Semantic Kompakkt Contact Privacy Policy

Use cases: "Give your Data more Meaning in all Dimensions"

One year programme with 8 partner projects testing the capacities of Semantic Kompakkt to enrich and make diverse data openly available

MK&G

M Deutsches
Schiffahrts
Museum

URBAN
COMPLEXITY
LAB

ETH zürich

DiBS
Digital Byzantine Studies

GBL Lehrstuhl für
Gebäudelehre
und Grundlagen
des Entwerfens | **RWTH AACHEN**
UNIVERSITY

Studio Stad

Extended presentation: Herrenhäuser des Ostseeraums

Extending the presentation capabilities of Semantic Kompakkt with Semantic MediaWiki

Map visualization in Wikibase of all manor houses in the dataset with coordinate locations.

3D interior capture of Fossesholm, Norway, is also available in Semantic Kompakkt.

Herrenhauszentrum
des Ostseeraums

<http://tinyurl.com/2ah9575r>

Föderierte Abfrage nach Personen aus der Herrenhauszentrum-Datenbank mit entsprechenden Einträgen in Wikidata und Factgrid, einschließlich Bildern und Factgrid IDs

media:Adrienne-lafayette-mw4967.jpg
Q147341
Adrienne Françoise de Noailles de L...

media:Alexander Pope by Michael ...
Q76445
Alexander Pope

media:Alexander Roslin - Self-Portr...
Q833488
Alexander Roslin

media:Portrait présumé d'Anas...
Q100587
Anastasie du Motier de-Lafayette

media:Anders Johan von Höpken, ...
Q176442
Anders Johan von Höpken

Herrenhäuser Query Service: Kauffmann - Self ...

media:Anna Petrovna of Russia by ...

media:Carl Fredrik Scheffer - riksrå...

media:Count Carl Gustaf Tessin. P...

media:Carl von Linné.jpg

Federation case study

Ogham Stone CIIC 81 at UCC Cork #4 as LOD Resource

Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

via <http://archaeosquirrels.cloud/?model=CO074-148---->

Squirrel Data | Linked Open Ogham | powered by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network Linked Ogham

81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project)^{EN}

<http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081>

The 81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) resource is powered by Static [GeoPubby](#) generated using the [SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin](#)

Search: Go **Download Options:** Format:

Description: comment:Ogham Stone, Ireland

Property	Value
disclosedAt (oghamonto:disclosedAt)	OS40000120 (fslid:OS40000120)
exactMatch (oghamonto:exactMatch)	Q106680733 (wde:Q106680733) [x]
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OghamStone (oghamonto:OghamStone) [x] OghamStone_Squirrel (oghamonto:OghamStone_Squirrel) [x] Resource (ldp:Resource) [x] Resource (Resource) [x]
comment (rdfs:comment)	Ogham Stone, Ireland (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
label (rdfs:label)	81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)

Metadata

Property	Value
identifier (dce:identifier)	81 (xsd:string)
creator (terms:creator)	0000-0002-3246-3531 (0000-0002-3246-3531) [x]
license (terms:license)	deed.de (deed.de) [x]
rightsHolder (terms:rightsHolder)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0000-0002-3246-3531 (0000-0002-3246-3531) [x] 0000-0003-4696-2101 (0000-0003-4696-2101) [x]
inDataset (void:inDataset)	Linked_Open_Ogham (fslid:Linked_Open_Ogham) [2481 oghamonto:disclosedAt]
wasAttributedTo (prov:wasAttributedTo)	PythonStonesCIIC (fslid:PythonStonesCIIC)
wasDerivedFrom (prov:wasDerivedFrom)	og_stones.csv (og_stones.csv) [x]
wasGeneratedBy (prov:wasGeneratedBy)	Y50000081_activity (fslid:Y50000081_activity)

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 NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph

[SPARQL](#) [Collections](#) [Repositories](#) [Terminologies](#) [Manual](#)

SPARQL endpoint /api/sparql (see [documentation](#))

Example queries:

```

1 PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
3 SELECT ?geo ?county ?stone ?stoneLabel WHERE {
4   ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
5   ?item rdfs:label ?label .
6   ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7   ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8   ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
9   ?c a oghamonto:County .
10  ?c rdfs:label ?county .
11  ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
12  ?stone rdfs:label ?stoneLabel .
13  FILTER (?stone = <http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081>)
14 }
    
```


Table Response 1 result

Simple view Ellipse Filter query results Page size: 50

geo	county	stone	stoneLabel
1 *POINT(-8.761667 51.816389)^^geo:wktLiteral	*Cork*@en	<http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081>	*81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project)*@en

Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entries

Federating between Semantic Kompakkt to get the 3D file view location & Wikidata to get all external IDs

Wikibase / Query Service Examples

Query Helper Filter

+ Show

- object of representation
- file view
- wikidata id

Limit

[Query source](#)

```
1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX wdqs: <https://query.wikidata.org/sparql>
4
5 SELECT DISTINCT ?CIIC81Label ?3D_view ?wd_id ?OSM_id ?SMRS_id ?LOD_id ?Factgrid_id WHERE {
6   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
7   VALUES ?CIIC81 {tib:Q1407}
8   ?Media_item tib:P63 ?CIIC81.
9   ?Media_item tib:P74 ?3D_view.
10  ?CIIC81 tib:P107 ?wd_id.
11
12  BIND(IRI(CONCAT(STR(wd:), ?wd_id)) AS ?wd_item)
13
14  SERVICE wdqs: {
15    ?wd_item wdt:P11693 ?OSM_id;
16    wdt:P4057 ?SMRS_id;
17    wdt:P2888 ?LOD_id;
18    wdt:P8168 ?Factgrid_id.
19  }
20 }
21
```

1 result in 513 ms </> Code

CIIC81Label	3D_view	wd_id	OSM_id	SMRS_id	LOD_id	Factgrid_id
Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/670e54210da6ec51ee08e5fb	Q130529871	11071361392	CO074-148----	http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081	Q1000294

Federating between Wikidata (to get external IDs), FactGrid (to get related people and inscriptions), and Fuzzy Spatial Locations (fuzzy-sl) to get coordinates

```

1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
4 PREFIX fslwd: <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/entity/>
5 PREFIX fslwdt: <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/prop/direct/>
6 PREFIX fg: <https://database.factgrid.de/entity/>
7 PREFIX fgt: <https://database.factgrid.de/prop/direct/>
8
9 SELECT ?label ?wikiq ?factgridq ?fslq ?inscription ?related_personsLabels ?coordinates ?osmnode ?smrid ?uri WHERE {
10 SERVICE <https://query.wikidata.org/sparql> {
11   ?wikiq wdt:P31 wd:Q2016147.
12   FILTER(?wikiq = wd:Q130529871)
13   ?wikiq rdfs:label ?label.
14   FILTER(LANG(?label) IN("en"))
15   ?wikiq wdt:P8168 ?factgridq;
16     wdt:P11693 ?osmnode;
17     wdt:P4057 ?smrid;
18     wdt:P2888 ?uri.
19 }
20 SERVICE <https://database.factgrid.de/sparql> {
21   fg:Q1000294 fgt:P1219 ?inscription;
22   fgt:P33 ?related_persons;
23   fgt:P1215 ?fslq.
24   ?related_persons rdfs:label ?related_personsLabels.
25   FILTER(LANG(?related_personsLabels) IN("en"))
26 }
27 SERVICE <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/query/sparql> { fslwd:Q74 fslwdt:P4 ?coordinates. }
28 }
    
```

<https://sparql.dblp.org/YKlrP3>

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

Query results: 2 lines found 11ms in total 11ms for computation 0.0ms for resolving and sending

	?label	?wikiq	?factgridq	?fslq	?inscription	?related_personsLabels	?coordinates	?osmnode	?smrid	?uri
1	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Q130529871	Q1000294	Q74	C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI	cassittas	Point(-8.492443111 51.893659305)	11071361392	CO074-148---	Y50000081
2	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Q130529871	Q1000294	Q74	C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI	Calliti	Point(-8.492443111 51.893659305)	11071361392	CO074-148---	Y50000081

Conclusion & Outlook

Challenges

- Frictionless federation remains challenging on both technical and social level
- Ontology harmonisation and mapping require community coordination across different disciplines
- AI-enhanced enrichment capabilities not fully explored

Opportunities

- Flexible data structure and possibility to express ambiguity and fuzziness
- Accessible user interfaces with granular read / write access
- Working Groups within individual consortia, the cross-cutting NFDI Section Metadata, active user communities around Wikidata and Wikibase

Finis!
Thx :-)

Questions?

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